

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) mj21348_0m

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: mj21348_0m

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0031 A	Wavelength=1.34139	
Cell:	a=7.1845 (2)	b=26.5672 (8)	c=17.0552 (5)
	alpha=90	beta=90	gamma=90
Temperature:	193 K		
	Calculated	Reported	
Volume	3255.36 (16)	3255.36 (16)	
Space group	C 2 2 21	C 2 2 21	
Hall group	C 2c 2	C 2c 2	
Moiety formula	2(C19 H17 N O3), H2 O [+ solvent]	C19 H17 N O3, 0.5(H2 O)	
Sum formula	C38 H36 N2 O7 [+ solvent]	C19 H18 N O3.50	
Mr	632.69	316.34	
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.291	1.291	
Z	4	8	
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.463	0.466	
F000	1336.0	1336.0	
F000'	1339.18		
h, k, lmax	8, 32, 20	8, 32, 20	
Nref	3112 [1775]	3100	
Tmin, Tmax	0.994, 0.995	0.618, 0.751	
Tmin'	0.977		

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.618 Tmax=0.751
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 1.75/1.00 Theta(max)= 54.892

R(reflections)= 0.0343 (2847)

wR2(reflections)=
0.0919 (3100)

S = 1.054

Npar= 222

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format
test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT911_ALERT_3_C Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & Sth/L= 0.600 11 Report

● **Alert level G**

ABSMU01_ALERT_1_G Calculation of _exptl_absorpt_correction_mu
not performed for this radiation type.

PLAT007_ALERT_5_G	Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms	1	Report
PLAT042_ALERT_1_G	Calc. and Reported Moiety Formula Strings Differ	Please	Check
PLAT045_ALERT_1_G	Calculated and Reported Z Differ by a Factor ...	0.50	Check
PLAT300_ALERT_4_G	Atom Site Occupancy of H1SA Constrained at	0.5	Check
PLAT300_ALERT_4_G	Atom Site Occupancy of H1SB Constrained at	0.5	Check
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O1	108.0	Degree
PLAT605_ALERT_4_G	Largest Solvent Accessible VOID in the Structure	18	A**3
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G	Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels	2	Note
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C1 (Sohnke SpGr)	R	Verify
PLAT913_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of Very Strong Reflections in FCF	2	Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G	Number of OMIT Records in Embedded .res File ...	2	Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.	0	Info
PLAT984_ALERT_1_G	The C-f'= 0.0148 Deviates from the B&C-Value	0.0137	Check
PLAT984_ALERT_1_G	The N-f'= 0.0253 Deviates from the B&C-Value	0.0241	Check
PLAT984_ALERT_1_G	The O-f'= 0.0412 Deviates from the B&C-Value	0.0389	Check

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
1 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
16 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

6 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
3 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
2 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
5 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

